

Chemical Reactivity and Light Absorption Part I.

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It can now be stated with a certain amount of definiteness that the appearance of a continuous absorption (non-quantised absorption) spectrum of a gas is always a case of photochemical dissociation taking place in the gas. Moreover, convergence limits and continuous absorption have up till now only been observed for those molecules in which the binding forces are appreciably weakened by absorption.

According to Kuhn and Franck, one normal and one excited metastable atom are produced from the dissociation of the halogen molecules. Naturally, more energy is required for this type of dissociation than in the cases where the products of dissociation are two normal atoms. Mecke (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1981, 27, 359) has drawn the following conclusion from his observations on molecular spectra and photochemical dissociation:

“ On the short wave side of the band convergence limit and in a spectral region distinguished by continuous absorption and by the fact that the molecules cease to fluoresce, a photochemical reaction with theoretical quantum yield can take place (chain reactions are of course excluded from this last statement). At the entrance to this region is a spectral region, more or less wide, in which the absorbed energy is not sufficient to produce primary dissociation but which nevertheless is large enough when transferred by impact, to produce dissociation by sensitising. In this spectral region as is usual for reactions with excited molecules we obtain only a fraction of the theoretical yield for quantum; as the convergence limit is approached, however, this yield rapidly attains the maximum value”.

The phenomenon of sensitised decomposition of simple molecules is more or less allied to the phenomenon of predissociation studied by Victor Henri with polyatomic molecules,

It appears, therefore that increase in the light absorption by a molecule is associated with its increased reactivity and loosening of the binding forces. Conversely when a molecule becomes more reactive, it is likely to absorb light more markedly. Henri (Compare Debye, "Structure of Molecules," Blackie & Son, 1932) has shown that the absorption spectra of a number of molecules pass from a fine structure to a blurred one consisting of diffuse bands in the short wave-length side of the spectrum. The condition of the molecule in which the bands are diffused has been called the *predissociation*, as it has been observed that in this condition the molecules are chemically reactive and can decompose. The limit of predissociation is assumed to set the upper limit of dissociation of a molecule.

Henri has reported that an increase of temperature displaces the limits of dissociation towards the visible region and the radiations of the region of predissociation causes photochemical reaction or chemical sensitisation of the molecules.

From the researches of Henri and others it is clear that on increasing the temperature, the amount of light absorption increases and the molecules dissociate on illumination by radiations of longer wave-lengths. Thus with acetaldehyde, the absorption spectrum at the laboratory temperature consists of large number of sharp bands with rotational structure between 3484 to 3050 $\overset{\circ}{\text{A}}$. Near 3050 $\overset{\circ}{\text{A}}$ the bands become blurred rapidly due to predissociation of the molecules and about 60 diffuse bands reaching upto 2823 $\overset{\circ}{\text{A}}$ have been measured. Also there is superimposed on these diffuse bands, a broad continuous band starting at about 3080 $\overset{\circ}{\text{A}}$ with a maximum at 2850 $\overset{\circ}{\text{A}}$ and subsequently falling off more and more on the ultraviolet side. If acetaldehyde vapour is heated to 200°, feeble diffuse bands appear between 3500 and 3200 $\overset{\circ}{\text{A}}$ with a strong continuous absorption reaching far into the ultraviolet.

When acetaldehyde vapour is illuminated at the laboratory temperature, decomposition takes place into CO and CH₄ only when the wave-length is 3002 $\overset{\circ}{\text{A}}$ or shorter; whilst at 200°, acetaldehyde vapour can be photolysed by radiations of wave-length exceeding 3100 $\overset{\circ}{\text{A}}$. According to Hinshelwood and Hutchinson (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1926, **A**, 111, 380), acetaldehyde vapour can be thermally decomposed at 430°. Similar behaviour has been observed with other aldehydes, CS₂, NH₃, NO₂, sulphur and other substances.

It appears, therefore, from these researches on photochemical decomposition and predissociation that the increase in the chemical reactivity of a substance by increase of temperature is associated with an increased light absorption, specially of ultraviolet light. Moreover, increased temperature of the molecules sensitises them towards their decomposition by longer wave-lengths. Hence the weakening of the binding forces of molecules and thus making them unstable is associated with increased light absorption by the molecules. These researches on predissociation and chemical decomposition have been solely confined to pure individual substances and not to mixtures with which chemists are mainly concerned. Let us examine the problem from the point of view of mixtures of two or more substances.

It is well known that in their experiments on the photochemical combination of hydrogen and chlorine, Bunsen and Roscoe reported that the absorption of light by chlorine was increased by the presence of hydrogen, although Burgess and Chapman (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 89, 1402) could not detect any difference in the absorption of pure chlorine or its mixture with air or hydrogen.

On the other hand, Weigert (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1926, 120, 215) has shown that radiations of mean wave-length 5900\AA , and Dhar and Bhagwat (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1930, 190, 415) have reported that radiations of wave-lengths $5750\text{-}5800\text{\AA}$, 6650\AA , and 7304\AA can accelerate the reaction between chlorine and hydrogen, although the calculated maximum wave-length capable of initiating the reaction has the value 5400\AA . This value has been obtained from the heat of dissociation of a gram molecule of chlorine having the value 52500 calories. According to Mecke (*loc. cit.*) the limits of sensitised decomposition and photochemical dissociation for chlorine molecules are 5000\AA and 4780\AA respectively.

Several years ago, Sirk (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1908, 61, 545) observed that chlorine and hydrogen combine in the dark when heated to 258° . The temperature coefficient of this thermal reaction has the value 1.6 for a 10 degree rise between 258° to 268° . On applying the Perrin-Lewis radiation hypothesis, the value $10,714\text{\AA}$ is obtained for the activation of the reaction. Moreover, Sachtleben (*Diss. Hannover*, 1914) obtained the temperature coefficient 2.04 for a 10° rise between $146^\circ.5$ and $160^\circ.1$ for the thermal reaction

between chlorine and hydrogen and hence the limiting wave-length obtained from this result is $11,110\text{\AA}$, a value almost identical to that of Sirk (compare Christiansen, *Z. physikal. Chem.* 1929 **B**, 2, 405). It appears, therefore, that the theoretical limiting wave-length for including the photochemical combination of chlorine and hydrogen is of the order of $10,000\text{\AA}$ and the experimental value is near 7000\AA . It is well known that a greater amount of energy is necessary for the photo-reaction than the thermal one with many decomposition reactions and a part of the light energy absorbed may be lost as fluorescence. It is of interest to note that Norrish (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 761; 1929, 1604, 1611) has concluded that far more energy is required to decompose nitrogen peroxide photochemically than thermally and has been able to observe fluorescence with nitrogen peroxide. Similarly fluorescence has been observed in acetaldehyde and acetone and formaldehyde vapour (cf. Leighton and Blacet, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **55**, 1766; Damon and Daniels, *ibid.*, 2363; Crone and Norrish, *Nature* 1933, **132**, 241; Herzberg and Franz, *Z. physik.*, 1932, **76**, 720). It is clear, therefore, from the foregoing remarks that the presence of hydrogen sensitises the decomposition of chlorine molecules and makes them reactive in radiations of longer wave-lengths. The careful measurements of the absorption spectra of chlorine by von Halban and Siedentopf (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1922, **103**, 71) show that the light absorption from yellow to red, reaches a maximum between 6140 to 6430\AA . It appears to the authors that accurate experiments on the absorption spectrum of a mixture of hydrogen and chlorine are likely to reveal that the absorption of light by chlorine is increased by the addition of hydrogen.

From our experiments on the kinetics of the iodine oxalate reaction, we have observed that the reaction is markedly accelerated by infra-red radiations of wave-lengths 8500\AA and 8750\AA and the maximum wave-length calculated from the temperature coefficient of the dark reaction was the value 8600\AA . The limits of sensitised decomposition and photochemical decomposition with iodine molecules are 8050\AA and 4995\AA respectively. It appears, therefore, that the presence of oxalate markedly sensitises the decomposition of iodine molecules, which become reactive in radiation of longer wave-lengths on the addition of oxalate using copper arc. We have carefully photographed the absorption spectra of $N/1700$ aqueous iodine

and $N/2$ -potassium oxalate solutions separately and a mixture containing 10 c.c. $N\text{-K}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ and 10 c.c. $N/850$ aqueous iodine and we find that the iodine solution alone shows almost complete absorption from 2700\AA , whilst with the oxalate solution complete absorption begins from 3000\AA . In the case of the mixture of the iodine and oxalate, almost complete absorption starts nearly from 3826\AA . These results, showing that the absorption of light by a solution of an oxalate is appreciably increased by the addition of dilute iodine solution, are of great interest from the view point of the nature of chemical reactivity.

In other words, the sensitisation of an oxalate solution by iodine is associated with marked increase of light absorption in the ultraviolet.

Many years ago Henri and Landau (*Compt. rend.*, 1913, 158, 181) showed that the absorption of ultraviolet light in the region $3200\text{-}2700\text{\AA}$ by a solution of oxalic acid is markedly increased by the addition of uranyl salts. Recently Ghosh and collaborators (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 353; 1928, 5, 191, 569) have carried on important quantitative measurements of the extinction coefficients of uranyl salts, ferric salts, and mercuric salts with varying concentrations of formic, acetic, propionic, oxalic, malonic, succinic, glycollic, lactic, tartaric, citric, and mandelic acids in the region $2300\text{-}3500\text{\AA}$ and have observed that the extinction coefficients of the mixtures of organic acids and the above salt solutions are always considerably greater than the sum of those of the organic acids and the salt solutions considered separately. Moreover, it is well known that almost all organic acids are oxidised by uranyl, ferric and mercuric salts even in presence of visible light.

Allmand and Reeve (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 2834) obtained the following quantum yields in the decompositions of oxalic and formic acid solutions used as sensitiser:

Wave-length in \AA ...	Oxalic acid.			Formic acid.		
	2650	3000	3650	2600	3000	3600
Quantum yield ...	0.0100	0.0041	0.00095	2.7	1.06	very small

The quantum yield of the decomposition of these acids is generally greater in the presence of the sensitisers.

It is not yet certain what the predissociation limits of acetic acid or the other organic acids are, but Henri has given the following values for some aldehydes.

Molecule.	Predissociation observed.	Cal.
H·CHO	2670 Å	107
CH ₃ CHO	3050	95
C ₆ H ₅ CHO	2550	110

Ghosh and collaborators (*loc. cit.*) have obtained the following results on light absorption with different organic acids.

M/20-Acid →	Formic	Acetic	Propionic	Oxalic	Malonic	Succinic
Beginning of absorption →	2445 Å	2445 Å	2445 Å	3274 Å	2507 Å	2445 Å
M/20-Acid →	Glycollic	Lactic	Tartaric	Mandelic		Citric
Beginning of absorption →	2722 Å	2507 Å	2600 Å	2800 Å	shorter than	2722 Å

It appears that these wave-lengths are predissociation limits of these organic acids in the gaseous states and they are decomposed in these radiations. It seems justifiable to apply the results obtained in the gaseous state to solutions because in many cases it has been observed that the absorption spectra of molecules in the gaseous state and in the dissolved condition are identical. Thus Urey, Dawsey and Rice (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 1371) have measured the absorption coefficients of a solution of hydrogen peroxide for wave-lengths from 3750-2150 Å and those of its vapour for wave-lengths 2150-2750 Å. The two absorption curves between 2150-2750 Å appear to be identical. Moreover, Allmand, Cunliffe and Maddison (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 655) have reported that the values of the extinction coefficient of chlorine in aqueous solution are very close to those of gaseous chlorine. Also in recent years it is being realised more and more that the kinetics of the chemical reactions taking place in solution are fundamentally the same as those of the same substances in the gaseous condition. Thus the decomposition of chlorine monoxide and the interaction of ozone

and chlorine occur at nearly the same velocity in carbon tetrachloride solution as in the gaseous state. Similarly the combinations of triethylamine and ethyl iodide and of acetic anhydride and ethyl alcohol take place at the same velocity in solution as in the gas phase (cf. Hinshelwood, *Ann. Rep. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, p. 43).

The absorption measurements of the solutions of organic acids carried on by Ghosh and co-workers show that oxalic acid has greater absorption in the near ultraviolet and it is well known that oxalic acid decomposes more readily in the same region.

Kailan (*Manatsh.*, 1913, 34, 1209) has found that when 0.5 to 2*N* solutions of acetic, oxalic, malonic, succinic, malic and tartaric acids are exposed to ultraviolet light from a quartz lamp, slight decomposition takes place. In recent communications Dhar and Atma Ram (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 287) and Dhar and Bhargava (*Nature*, 1933, 132, 30) have shown that aqueous solutions of organic acids decompose even in sunlight and the decomposition is accelerated in presence of oxygen. The decomposition velocity increases with the introduction of an alcoholic hydroxyl group in the molecule. Ferric and uranyl salts and also mercuric chloride accelerate these decompositions. Moreover, the researches of Ghosh and his collaborators show that the addition of uranium nitrate, ferric chloride or mercuric chloride markedly increases the light absorption of these organic acids. Here again we find that the weakening of the binding forces of molecules is associated with increased light absorption.

In publications from these laboratories we have shown that the oxidation of several organic acids by chromic acid or potassium permanganate is markedly accelerated by manganese salts and that these reactions are increased in light. We have made careful measurements of absorption spectra of the mixtures of organic acids with chromic acid or potassium permanganate, with or without the addition of manganese sulphate and we have observed that in all cases addition of manganese sulphate markedly increases the light absorption.

It has already been stated that the predissociation limit of benzaldehyde is $2550\overset{\circ}{\text{Å}}$. De Hemptinne (*J. Phys. Radium*, 1928, vi, 9, 357) has shown that the photolysis of benzaldehyde by radiations shorter than $2600\overset{\circ}{\text{Å}}$ takes place as follows:

The hydrogen reacts with the phenyl group to form benzene. The energy necessary for this decomposition is calculated to be 115780 cal corresponding to radiations of wave-length $2461\overset{\circ}{\text{Å}}$. This is the wave-length at which the total absorption band of benzaldehyde spectrum begins. Between $400\text{--}500^\circ$ benzaldehyde decomposes thermally. The decrease in the light energy necessary for decomposition at the higher temperatures is of the same order of magnitude as the increase in the vibrational energy of the benzaldehyde molecule as calculated from the variation in the specific heat with temperature. On the other hand in presence of oxygen, benzaldehyde undergoes oxidation even in the dark and rapidly in visible light. Bäckström (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **51**, 90) has shown that in the photo-oxidation of benzaldehyde in radiations of wave-lengths $3660\text{--}2536\overset{\circ}{\text{Å}}$ a very large quantum yield is obtained. Similarly Haber and Wansbrough-Jones (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1932, **B**, 18, 103) have reported that a solution of sodium sulphite produces hydrogen in only short ultraviolet light. In presence of oxygen, however, the sodium sulphite undergoes chemical change in the dark and markedly in light with an abnormally high quantum yield. Moreover, the photo-decompositions of iodoform, chloroform, ethyl iodide, methyl iodide, hydroiodic acid, etc., are greatly accelerated in presence of oxygen. All these results show that increase in chemical reactivity is always associated with light absorption.

From the foregoing discussion it will be evident that the controversy regarding the minimum frequency of radiations capable of initiating the chlorine—hydrogen reaction loses much of its significance because in presence of hydrogen the Cl—Cl linking is weakened and hence radiations of wave-lengths greater than $5000\overset{\circ}{\text{Å}}$, which are the limit of sensitised decomposition of chlorine molecules, can initiate the chemical change. With numerous photochemical reactions involving molecules of chlorine, bromine or iodine we have observed that radiations of wave-lengths 7304, 8500 and $8700\overset{\circ}{\text{Å}}$ are capable of initiating these reactions with halogens and reducing agents. This happens because due to the presence of reducing agents, the binding forces of the halogen molecules are considerably weakened and they are readily broken up either by increase of temperature or illumination and in many cases, increased light absorption has been observed with the mixtures. Hence the reactivity of a mixture is preceded by the formation of an additive product with weakening

of the binding forces and increased light absorption. It has been postulated that in the photochemical reactions involving the halogens, the primary change is the atomisation of the halogen molecules but the foregoing discussion shows that the first stage is the formation of an additive compound, may be of an unstable nature having an increased light absorption and this leads to the weakening of the binding forces of the halogen molecules.

In a recent communication Bhattacharyya and Dhar (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1932, 209, 123) have shown that $N/10$ solutions of trichloroacetic acid decomposes at 45° or higher temperatures in radiations of wave-lengths 6235, 4700, 4000, 3340, 3536, 3521, 3125\AA . The reaction in the dark at 50° is exceedingly slow. The velocity of the reaction in ultraviolet light is much greater than in visible light. From measurements on light absorption of aqueous solutions of trichloroacetic acid it is seen that there is appreciable absorption in the visible spectrum but the absorption is greatly increased in the ultraviolet, where marked absorption begins from 3200\AA and complete absorption from 3100. The dissociation energies of the linkings C—Cl, C—Br, C—I are 73.2, 60, 42.8 cal respectively. It is not definitely known whether C—Cl or C—O or O—H link is broken when trichloroacetic acid is illuminated but it is quite certain that ultraviolet radiation is necessary to break these links. As the experimental results show that trichloroacetic acid solutions are decomposed even by visible light, it appears that in presence of water, the above links are weakened and the whole reaction appears to be photosensitised by the presence of water.

Recently, Bowen and Tietz (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 234) have observed that the photo-oxidation of acetaldehyde, when dissolved in water by oxygen, is greater than in the gaseous state. Hence again the C=O or O—H link seems to be weakened by the presence of water. Moreover, it is well known that peroxides, which are addition products of the reacting aldehydes with oxygen are at first formed when aldehydes are brought in contact with oxygen.

It was generally believed that several bimolecular thermal reactions taking place in solution possessed velocities smaller than those calculated according to the expression (number of collisions) $\times e^{-E/RT}$.

This expression can predict the correct order of magnitude of numerous gaseous reactions depending on collisions. It has now been observed that there are several reactions in solution in which

the velocities are in agreement with the calculated values but there are other reactions in the dissolved state in which the observed velocity is much greater than the calculated one (cf. Moelwyn-Hughes, *Phil. Mag.*, 1932, vii, 14, 112). These are cases of sensitisation in presence of water. It is well known that many chemical changes are accelerated by the presence of moisture. Dhar (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1926, 159, 103) has suggested that in many photochemical reactions a cluster containing an ion and the reacting substances is formed in presence of moisture. Lewis (*Nature*, 1928, 121, 792) has reported that clustering takes place in the photochemical decomposition of nitrous oxide. Recently Forbes and collaborators (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 588) have advanced the view that photochemically efficient clusters are formed in the photo-oxidation of quinine by chromic acid in presence of sulphuric acid.

Kistiakowsky (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 49, 2194) has reported that intensive drying of chlorine gas does not effect its light absorption. The experimental observations of Rodebush and Klingelhofer (*Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.*, 1932, 18, 531) and Allmand and Craggs (*Nature*, 1932, 130, 927) seem to show that drying causes no inhibition of the chlorine—hydrogen reaction.

In recent years the existence of free OH radical as an intermediate product has been assumed by numerous workers in many chemical reactions and flames. Moreover, it has been postulated that in the reaction of hydrogen atoms with oxygen molecules, the first stage consists of an associative reaction between these atoms and oxygen molecules (cf. Bates and Lavin, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 81).

It is of interest to note that OH radical possesses many absorption lines in its spectrum in the region 3080 to 3267 $\overset{\circ}{\text{A}}$ whilst hydrogen and oxygen show no absorption in this region. Further work in this line is in progress in this laboratory.

SUMMARY.

1. From recent researches on photo-dissociation and predissociation, it can be concluded that in general, an increase in the light absorption by a molecule is associated with its increased chemical reactivity and weakening of the binding forces and conversely when

a molecule becomes more reactive, it is likely to absorb light more markedly.

2. Increase of temperature enhances the amount of light absorption and activity of the molecule and it decomposes on illumination by radiations of longer wave-lengths.

3. The presence of hydrogen sensitises the dissociation of chlorine molecules and makes them reactive in radiations of longer wave-lengths.

4. The addition of an oxalate markedly sensitises the decomposition of molecules of iodine and they are activated in the dark and in radiations of longer wave-lengths. The absorption of light by a solution of an oxalate is appreciably increased by the addition of dilute iodine solution.

5. In presence of uranium nitrate, ferric chloride or mercuric chloride, the light absorption and photo-decomposition of organic acids are greatly increased.

6. When manganese salts are added, the light absorption by mixtures of organic acids and chromic acid or potassium permanganate is increased and the oxidation of the organic acids by chromic acid or potassium permanganate is accelerated by the addition of manganese salts.

7. In presence of reducing agents like hydrogen, carbon monoxide, ferrous salts, nitrite, hydroxylamine, hydrazine, alcohols, acetone, organic acids and their salts, etc., the halogen molecules become reactive even in the dark and in radiations of wave-lengths longer than those necessary for their sensitised or photochemical dissociation, because the binding forces of the halogen molecules are considerably weakened due to the reducing agents.

8. The presence of water may sensitise the photo-decomposition of some substances by weakening the binding forces and increasing the light absorption.

9. It appears that the first stage in a reaction between two or more molecules, is the formation of an additive product with weakening of the linkages and increased light absorption. This is likely to happen in thermal as well as in photochemical reactions.

